

**INDUSTRY-ACADEME PARTNERSHIP AND PERFORMANCE LEVEL IN WORK
IMMERSION OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS IN CALABARZON: BASIS FOR
PROPOSED SHS WORK IMMERSION FRAMEWORK**

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ABSTRACT

This study entitled the *Industry-Academe Partnership and Performance Level in Work Immersion of Senior High School Learners in CALABARZON: Basis for Proposed SHS Work Immersion Framework* was conducted to determine the industry-academe partnership and performance level in work immersion of senior high school learners in CALABARZON. Specifically, it sought to answer the subsequent questions such as; the level of the industry-academe partnership of SHS work immersion in CALABARZON in terms of industry to academe (market aligned courses, develop skilled manpower, solutions for concerns and operational approach) academe to industry (funding and Infrastructure, equal partnership, placements and feasible goals); the performance level of senior high school learners in work immersion in CALABARZON in terms of teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, judgment and decision making, dependability and reliability, attitude and professionalism; the significant relationship between industry-academe partnership and the performance level of senior high school learners in work immersion in CALABARZON; and SHS work immersion framework related to industry-academe partnership and performance of senior high school learners can be proposed based on the result of the study.

The study employed the descriptive-correlational method of research and used purposive sampling techniques to select respondents, which included industry partners, work immersion teachers and SHS learners in CALABARZON. Data were analyzed using frequency and percentage distributions, weighted arithmetic mean, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson correlation coefficient. The study results indicated no significant differences in partnership aspects among

industry organizations or academe institutions, except for the impact of duration of operation on setting feasible goals. The relationship between Industry-Academe Partnership and SHS learner performance uncovers nuanced correlations, with placement quality linked to specific performance aspects.

The result of the research study paved the way for the emergence of the FSB Work Immersion Framework. This framework aims to better prepare students for their future careers and create a more enriching educational experience.

Keywords: *Industry-Academe Partnership, SHS Performance Level, Work Immersion, CALABARZON Region*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important and efficient methods of transforming an individual into an asset for industry is education. In today's world, where technical advancements play a vital role in society, educational enhancement is crucial. This is because knowledge cannot be replaced by any other means when it comes to keeping pace with modern civilization.

The Senior High School (SHS) Work Immersion program is a crucial component of the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines. The program aims to prepare SHS graduates for higher education, employment, middle-level skills development, and entrepreneurship. The Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) track with strands that include Home Economics, among others, provides learners with the necessary skills and competences to prepare them to face the challenges of the 21st Century. After the program, SHS graduates are expected to have fully acquired the following 21st century skills: (a) learning and innovation skills, (b) effective communication skills, information, media, and technology skills, and (d) life and career skills. In SY 2017-2018, the first batch of approximately 1.2 million SHS students graduated in April 2018. A majority of 82.67% of the graduates pursued higher education while 10.22% got employed. Only a small percentage engaged in entrepreneurship (1.30%) and middle-level skills development (0.42%). 5.39 % of the graduates did not pursue any of the exits after SHS graduation. The Work Immersion program provides learners with access to industry partners' facilities and employment simulation, where they are given opportunities to apply their competencies, gain practical industrial skills, and develop good work ethics and values relevant to pursuing further education and/or joining the world of work. The Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) also provides certification for learners who have completed the Work Immersion program.

The Department of Education (DepEd) has issued guidelines for the Career Guidance Program for S.Y. 2020 – 2021. The program aims to guide secondary level students in choosing career tracks that they intend to pursue through informed career choices towards becoming productive and contributing individuals as stated in RA 10533 otherwise known as the Basic Education Act of 2013. The guidelines and procedures shall guide all stakeholders in planning, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of the Career Guidance Program for S.Y. 2020 -2021. The K to 12 curriculum is designed to holistically prepare learners to become effective in helping address the needs of the nation, by pursuing either higher education, employment, entrepreneurship, or middle-level skills development. Competence in work immersion is crucial for students' seamless entry into professional settings. Academic knowledge forms the foundation, helping students grasp industry-specific concepts, while hands-on skills acquired during work immersion facilitate

the practical application of knowledge, fostering adaptability and problem-solving. Attitude is paramount, shaping students' approaches to tasks, collaboration, and challenges.

Order No. 30 of the DepEd, s. According to the 2017 Guidelines for Work Immersion, one of the objectives of the K–12 Basic Education Program is to help learners develop the skills, work ethics, and values necessary for continuing their education and, or entering the workforce. To better align the nation's development goals with the primary education system. Work Immersion has been added as a mandatory subject to the curriculum. This course gives students a chance to practice applying their competencies in their areas of specialization and applicable disciplines in real-world professional settings, as well as to become familiar with the workplace. Additionally, according to DepEd Order 30, students must complete the work immersion program to graduate from Senior High School.

The researcher, who serves as the work-immersion focal person, identified several concerns that need to be addressed, particularly in the TVL Home Economics strand/specialization, throughout the program's four-year implementation in the local area. Three issues were discovered through informal interviews and observation. First off, due to their busy schedules with teaching assignments, work commitments, and other community obligations, teachers are unable to observe their students regularly throughout the work immersion. According to the researcher's formal interviews, some students have a poor work orientation, which lowers their productivity on the tasks they are given. Lastly, the observation instrument employed lacks sufficient job specificity to address all the competencies listed in the Curriculum Guide.

With this, the researcher would like to determine the industry-academe partnership and performance level in work immersion of Senior High School learners in CALABARZON as the basis for the proposed SHS work immersion framework.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the industry-academe partnership and performance level in work immersion of Senior High School learners in CALABARZON as the basis for the proposed SHS work immersion framework. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the level of the industry-academe partnership of SHS work immersion in CALABARZON in terms of the following aspects:

- 1.1 industry to academe
 - 1.1.1 market aligned courses
 - 1.1.2 develop skilled manpower
 - 1.1.3 solutions for concerns
 - 1.1.4 operational approach
- 1.2 academe to industry
 - 1.2.1 funding and infrastructure
 - 1.2.2 equal partnership
 - 1.2.3 placements
 - 1.2.4 feasible goals?

2. What is the performance level of senior high school learners in work immersion in CALABARZON in terms of the following competencies:

- 2.1 teamwork
- 2.2 communication
- 2.3 attendance and punctuality

- 2.4 productivity and resilience
- 2.5 initiative and proactivity
- 2.6 judgment and decision making
- 2.7 dependability and reliability
- 2.8 attitude
- 2.9 professionalism?

3. Is there a significant relationship between industry-academe partnership and the performance level of senior high school learners in work immersion in CALABARZON?

4. What SHS work immersion framework could be proposed by the researcher relative to industry-academe partnership and performance level of senior high school learners in CALABARZON?

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive-correlational research method was utilized in the conduct of the study. Descriptive research methodology is a fundamental research technique that analyzes the situation as it is in the present, according to Leedy & Ormrod in 2019. In descriptive research, characteristics of a specific event are identified based on observation, or correlations between two or more phenomena are investigated.

Participants

Sampling or purposive was used to determine the public senior high schools that offer Technical Vocational Track with Home Economics as its strand/specialization, requiring students to complete their work immersion. To determine the number of samples representing the population, the students enrolled in each School offering Technical Vocational Livelihood Track with Home Economics as its strand/specialization, selected alumni of the same track and strand, industry partners, and work immersion teachers were taken as samples of the study.

Instruments of the Study

A self-made survey-questionnaire was the main instrument used in this study by the researcher. The questionnaire was divided into four parts. The survey questionnaire employed in the conduct of research the study enables to gather a reliable needed data, the researcher formulated the questions based on several articles in the related concepts, literatures and studies that are similar with the present study. Part I is the elicited information about the level of the industry-academe partnership of senior high school learners regarding market aligned courses, develop skilled manpower, solutions for concerns, operational approach, funding and infrastructure, equal partnership, placements, and feasible goals. Part II, students in senior high school were asked to rate their level of performance in a variety of areas, including teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, productivity and resilience, initiative and proactivity, judgment and decision-making, dependability and reliability, attitude, and professionalism.

Procedure

To facilitate access to respondents' institutions, the researcher-initiated correspondence with the Department of Education (DepEd) CALABARZON Region, headed by Regional Director Atty. Alberto T. Escobarte. Additionally, letters of request were obtained from the Schools Division Superintendents of seven Schools Division Offices (SDOs) across the region. Upon approval, the researcher presented the permit to District Supervisors, who endorsed it to principals and work immersion teachers for cooperation in conducting the survey. Seeking guidance, the researcher involved their dissertation adviser and field experts to evaluate the survey instrument. Professional feedback formed the basis for refining the questionnaire through amendments, exclusions, deletions, and revisions. All communication and the finalized Google form link were documented. Respondents were then requested to complete the survey questionnaire, with collected data subsequently tallied, coded, collated, and tabulated. The researcher employed appropriate statistical tools to analyze and interpret the gathered information.

RESULTS

This section provides the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data relative to the industry-academe partnership and performance level of senior high school work immersion learners in the CALABARZON Region.

Level of Industry-Academe Partnership of SHS Work Immersion in CALABARZON in terms of Industry to Academe Partnership

Table 1.1

Mean Scores of the Level of Industry-Academe Partnership of SHS Work Immersion in CALABARZON in terms of Industry to Academe Partnership

The industry-academe partnership...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.1.1 Market Aligned Courses	3.67	High Level of Partnership
1.1.2 Develop Skilled Courses	3.45	High Level of Partnership
1.1.3 Solutions for Concerns	2.99	Medium Level of Partnership
1..1.4 Operational Approach	3.53	High Level of Partnership

Partnership Level of Industry-Academe Partnership of SHS Work Immersion in CALABARZON in terms of Academe to Industry Partnership

Table No. 1.2

Mean Scores of the Partnership Level of Industry-Academe Partnership of SHS Work Immersion in CALABARZON in terms of Academe to Industry Partnership

The academe-industry partnership...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1.2.1 Funding and Infrastructure	2.63	Medium Level of Partnership

1.2.2 Equal Partnership	4.03	High Level of Partnership
1.2.3 Placements	3.43	Medium Level of Partnership
1.2.4 Feasible Goals	3.67	High Level of Partnership

Performance Level of Senior High School Learners in Work Immersion in CALABARZON

Table 2

Mean Scores of the Level of Performance of Senior High School Learners in Work Immersion

The learners...	Industry Partners	Work Immersion Teachers	Work Immersion Learners	Overall Mean	Verbal Interpretation
2.1 Teamwork	4.07	4.11	4.13	4.11	Very Satisfactory
2.2 Communication	4.00	3.99	3.63	3.87	Very Satisfactory
2.3 Attendance and Punctuality	3.90	3.60	3.86	3.79	Very Satisfactory
2.4 Productivity and Resilience	3.70	3.37	3.54	3.54	Very Satisfactory
2.5 Initiative and Proactivity	3.57	3.47	3.72	3.59	Very Satisfactory
2.6 Judgement and Decision Making	3.50	3.57	3.57	3.55	Very Satisfactory
2.7 Dependability and Reliability	3.61	3.69	3.70	3.67	Very Satisfactory
2.8 Attitude	3.61	3.66	4.06	3.78	Very Satisfactory
2.9 Professionalism	3.74	3.77	3.63	3.71	Very Satisfactory

DISCUSSION

The mean score, standing at 3.67 and categorized as a "High Level of Partnership," highlights the overall strength of the Industry-Academe Partnership in CALABARZON when it comes to aligning industry to academe with market-aligned courses. The table revealed that it agrees with the notion that the Work-Immersion Program, known as the Work-Based Learning (WBL) opportunity, is a program implemented for job simulation wherein the students can apply what they have learned and gives them the idea of the competencies on their future college plans (Alfeld, 2018). In terms of skilled manpower, the mean of 3.53 and labeled as a "High Level of Partnership" implies that the partnership is effective in focusing on essential employability skills, instilling a positive attitude toward continuous learning, and promoting a strong commitment to work and quality results. The expectations of the employer nowadays have changed with the new emerging trends of industries. Today, newly hired are not judged on their academic performance or technical and behavioral skills but on a new set of non-cognitive skills which have taken precedence. The way of looking at these skills has changed, but the concept still exists (Chakrabarty, 2018). With regards to solutions for concerns, the industry to academe is seldom partnership as resulted by the grand mean of 2.99 and categorized as a "Medium Level of Partnership". This suggests that the partnership is moderately effective in approaching concerns with practical strategies, embracing open-mindedness, and actively engaging in coordinated efforts to implement solutions. As the Oxford University Press ELT (2018) supported, students' independence will be developed when they are provided an opportunity to lead their learning through self-learning practice that allows students to perform independently. The grand mean score, standing at 3.53 and falling within the "High Level of Partnership" range, concerns the operational approach. This suggests that the partnership is highly effective in promoting an environment of continuous development, ensuring efficient daily operations, and

prioritizing familiarity with the company's organizational structure. Because operation management is a management task, it involves managing people, equipment, technology, information, and all other resources required in the production of goods and services. Operational management is the central main task of each company. Regardless of the size of the company, whether it is in the industry, whether it is manufacturing or service, or for profit or not for profit. (Sanders, 2018).

The mean score, standing at 2.63 and falling within the "High Level of Partnership" range, reflects funding and infrastructure support. The partnership is highly effective in ensuring comprehensive infrastructure and prioritizing student well-being through safe and clean workplace facilities. Facilities and infrastructure have a significant influence on the internship program because the implementation of the apprenticeship program is only about three months for university entrants and even much less for immersion programs. The mean score of 4.03 and falling within the "High Level of Partnership" range concerns equal partnership. This suggests that the partnership is highly effective in providing valuable learning opportunities and fostering engagement outside the traditional classroom setting. Partnerships are essential for educational institutions to minimize their dependence on physical resources, facilitate training and employment for its students, match their curricular offerings to the needs of the industry, and maintaining a reputable image. The mean, which is 3.43, reflects a medium level of partnership for the entirety of the evaluated aspects. This suggests that the partnership level between academe and industry in CALABARZON, concerning Placements, is moderate. While there are areas of strength, there are also areas where enhancements could be made to elevate the overall partnership level. Students gain valuable real-world experience, and this reduces the adjustment period, which is required when starting employment. The mean, which is 3.67, reflects a high level of partnership for the entirety of the evaluated aspects related to Feasible Goals. Tracey et. al (2018) assert the relationship between the business and the local school system involves multiple stakeholders operating in a reciprocal relationship that accomplishes mutual goals. That stated business leaders want to partner with schools in a way that is more meaningful than surface-level sponsorship.

SHS work immersion learners demonstrated a very satisfactory level of teamwork, as indicated by the cumulative mean score of 4.11. They exhibited respect and consideration for their team members, actively engaged in tasks, and consistently worked together to fulfill their responsibilities and achieve goals. According to Graft (2021), when trainees begin to work together, the different groups and skill sets will unavoidably spark new ideas. These fresh viewpoints and talks that result from cooperation can generate original concepts that can easily accomplish the goals of the team and lead your company to higher overall success. The learners in work immersion demonstrated strong communication skills, with a mean of 3.87. They excelled in attentive listening, consistently providing accurate verbal and written information, crafting grammatical sounds and logically structured written communication. Ratunil (2017) said that there is a need to be skilled in interpersonal communication among the SHS students and stresses the crucial role of the partnership in the implementation and achievement of the goal of the SHS Program. The mean for all aspects of attendance and punctuality was 3.79, indicating a very satisfactory overall performance. Learners demonstrated consistent punctuality, maintained good attendance records, arrived at work on time, and completed assignments within deadlines. O'Neill (2020) highlights that a trainee should pay attention to timeliness and attendance to be able to increase work performance. To increase performance and productivity, senior high school training is primarily driven by this goal. The SHS work immersion learners achieved a very satisfactory score in terms of productivity and resilience, with a mean of 3.54. They were able to manage time efficiently, multitask, and incorporate an optimistic mindset; but

there is a need for improvement in delivering high-quality outcomes, achieving desired results under pressure, and showing consistent resilience in the face of difficulties or obstacles. The importance of strengthening the behavior of resiliency students to achieve high productivity is to prepare them to operate effectively in the volatile, uncertain, and complex world of work (Marinova, 2017). With a mean of 3.59, the capability to autonomously complete their responsibilities, paid close attention to supervisor instructions, and were proactive in identifying and addressing opportunities and challenges. These results lend credence to Kolb's experiential learning theory, which holds that learning happens most effectively when a person moves through a cycle of four stages: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (Kolb, 1984, Cherry, 2018). The computed mean was 3.59 described as 'Very Satisfactory'. In terms of judgment and decision-making, SHS work immersion learners with a mean of 3.55. They demonstrated the ability to critically analyze essential information, take responsibility for mistakes and deficiencies, and consider personal experiences and others' opinions when making decisions. Many studies show that decision-making skills must start at an early age if they want to enhance their chance of a good job in the future. And the emergence of employability skills is attributed to different skills learned inside the classroom such as communication skills, problem-solving skills, and decision-making skills (Asonitou, 2018). SHS work immersion learners achieved a very satisfactory performance in dependability and reliability, with a mean of 3.67. They showcased commitment to their responsibilities, adaptability to changes in the workplace, and proficiently completed tasks in a timely manner. The objectives of the WIP are to hone the skills and immerse the students in their chosen curriculum exits. For the attainment of their lifelong skills, being reliable and dependable is among the most sought characteristics in a workplace (Shannon Staffing Working Together, 2018). The learners achieved a very satisfactory score in terms of attitude, with an overall mean of 3.78. They possessed a positive attitude towards work, demonstrated regard and sensitivity to the feelings of others, took pride in their work, and offered help voluntarily. Attitude is important in the realization of the goals for the different curriculum exits, for those who are planning to enroll in college it was found that attitudes share a relationship with the success of the composition of First Year *Kolehiyo* students (Russo, 2018). The learners used tools, equipment, and all facilities properly, followed all rules and guidelines when conflicts arose and considered physical characteristics that met placement and work needs. Professionalism is not only limited to the culture in one workplace but also entails values that require one trainee or employee to advance in terms of career by enhancing a high degree of ethical behavior (San Luis, 2018).

The only significant relationship found in this analysis is between placements and teamwork performance, indicating that placements have a significant negative impact on teamwork performance. It is important to note that teamwork provides opportunities for employees to achieve both personal and professional growth. This is because working in teams often requires cooperation and interaction among learners from different departments and with different personalities or skill sets. Over time, teamwork can help all employees of an organization work better together and become more adaptable when common or shared goals are involved (Graft, 2021). There is no correlation (r value of 0.000) between industry-academe partnership indicators and communication. Ratunil (2017) said that there is a need to be skilled in interpersonal communication among SHS students and stresses the crucial role of the partnership in the implementation and achievement of the goal of the SHS Program. For this reason, education aims to equip every learner with the necessary knowledge and skills needed to conquer the world (Lintag – Ilgan, 2018). A significant relationship is found between placements and attendance and punctuality, indicating that placements have a significant positive impact on these aspects. Other factors do not show significant relationships with attendance and punctuality. Students gain valuable real-world experience, and this reduces the

adjustment period, which is required when starting employment. For example, interns do not need as much socialization, training, and time for adjustment as new recruits (Maertz et al., 2018).

Caraig (2018) that attendance like all work ethics affects every aspect of the workplace and the business. Being on time has a positive impact on learning. In a study conducted by Calderella et. al 2011 as cited by Vukovic (2019), being late or absent can disrupt learning. There is no significant relationship between the industry-academe partnership indicators and productivity and resilience. In a study by the *Frontiers in Psychology*, it was found that when good behavior and resilience are not well controlled, it can result in high levels of stress and ultimately cause negative results (Rees et.al, 2015). The importance of strengthening the behavior of resiliency students to achieve high productivity is to prepare them to operate effectively in the volatile, uncertain, and complex world of work (Marinova, 2017). There is no statistically significant relationship with the initiative and proactivity of senior high school learners during their work immersion. According to Geertshuis et al. (2017), "Proactivity is important to individual success" in addition, the Institute of Progressive Education & Learning (2018), further explained that the Curriculum Standards of the K-12 is to develop the societal soft skills of students, to be more pro-active response in the task and activities given to the 21st Century Learners. A strong positive correlation is found between student placements and their judgment and decision-making skills. This suggests that student placements significantly influence how well they make judgments and decisions during work immersion. The main aim of the internship is to provide an opportunity for undergraduate students to learn from practical experience and solve real-world problems in the workplace, as well as to foster mutually beneficial relationships between the industry and the university (Staehr et al., 2019). There is no significant relationship between the academe-industry partnership indicators and students' dependability and reliability. The objectives of the WIP are to hone the skills and immerse the students in their chosen curriculum exits. For the attainment of their lifelong skills, being reliable and dependable is among the most sought characteristics in a workplace (Shannon Staffing Working Together, 2018). Academe-industry partnership doesn't strongly impact students' attitude. In any business establishments on their marketability of those interns' ethical behavior such as accepting criticism constructively is important (Gault 2018), a life skill essential for the curriculum exit of *Trabaho*. This implies that work attitude is relative to their overall performance in a workplace, thus, if one has the right attitude, communicating regarding concerns or ideas will be much easier and more open. The operational approach only has a statistically significant relationship with the professionalism of senior high school learners during their work immersion. This factor significantly influences how professional students are perceived to be. Success in the workplace work culture and professionalism is crucial since professionalism integrates all aspects of professional appearances and workplace culture (Coker, 2018).

Conclusions

The study indicates a strong partnership on market-aligned practices, practical learning, and fostering a positive attitude toward continuous learning. In the partnership between academe and industry, areas such as funding, infrastructure, attendance, and learner engagement showcase a high level of collaboration. There is a significant partnership in providing students with real-world work experiences for their personal and professional growth. However, there are challenges, notably in providing transportation allowances for work immersion learners, indicating a need for improvement in this specific area.

The performance evaluation of Senior High School learners in work immersion in CALABARZON reveals overall very satisfactory performance in various aspects of teamwork, communication, punctuality, task execution, decision-making, task completion, and willingness to help. These findings provide valuable insights into the strengths and areas for growth of SHS learners in work immersion, offering opportunities for targeted improvement strategies.

There is a significant positive correlation between placements and teamwork, communication, attendance and punctuality, and judgment and decision-making, indicating that the quality of placements is linked to these aspects of learner performance. Additionally, a moderate positive correlation is found between industry-academe partnership and communication, attendance and punctuality, and productivity and resilience, suggesting that a stronger partnership is associated with better performance in these areas. However, no significant relationships were found in terms of initiative and proactivity, dependability and reliability, and attitude, except for a moderate negative correlation between skilled manpower development and attitude. These findings highlight the nuanced relationship between industry-academe partnership and SHS learner performance, with specific areas showing stronger connections than others, providing valuable insights for improving work immersion programs.

The proposed SHS Work Immersion Framework, encapsulated in the FSB SHS Work Immersion Framework, emerges as a comprehensive and well-rounded program designed to cultivate the holistic development of students. The core components of knowledge, attitude, skills, and placement synergistically contribute to a robust experiential learning experience. Parental and guardian involvement and support play a crucial role in providing a strong foundation for students, fostering a supportive ecosystem that extends beyond the educational institution. Academic delivery and management are paramount in aligning theoretical knowledge with practical applications. Furthermore, the incorporation of student self-rating and reflection encourages learners to introspect and gauge their personal growth throughout the immersion process. This self-awareness is instrumental in shaping their career aspirations and refining their skill sets. The industry monitoring and feedback mechanisms serve as a bridge between

academia and industry to offer valuable insights into the relevance of the curriculum. The framework anticipates diverse career paths for the learners' post-work immersion, including avenues in employment, entrepreneurship, middle-level skills development, and higher education. This forward-looking approach aligns with the ever-changing landscape of the workforce, preparing students to navigate and contribute meaningfully to their chosen fields.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher recommends the following:

1. Academic institutions may focus on enhancing market-aligned practices, practical learning, and fostering a positive attitude. Develop programs exploring business concepts, expanding learning opportunities, and boosting confidence. Nurture thoughtful conflict resolution, understanding of company structures, and active student engagement. Address funding, infrastructure, attendance, and learner engagement urgently. Immediate strategies for transportation allowances are crucial. These measures will ensure comprehensive partnership, enhancing student growth and preparing them for the future.
2. Regional Director in CALABARZON and Schools Division Superintendent in the entire region may consider using the results of the study (FSB Work Immersion Framework) as basis of designing targeted interventions focusing on specific areas for improvement identified in the performance evaluation. Implement effective partnership through training programs emphasizing effective problem-solving and constructive feedback acceptance. Incorporate regular reflection exercises and mentorship programs to enhance performance and skills.
3. Work immersion teachers may strengthen quality placements, ensuring they align closely with the curriculum to enhance learner teamwork and communication skills. Foster stronger industry-academe partnerships, focusing on communication, attendance, punctuality, and resilience skills. Address the negative correlation between skilled manpower development and attitude through targeted training programs.
4. Parents, academe, students, and industry partners may foster a supportive learning environment by actively involving in the work immersion program. Enhance curriculum alignment with industry needs, focusing on teacher training and real-world integration. Encourage self-assessment and reflection among students, promoting personal growth. Strengthen industry partner mentorship through clear expectations and feedback loops, enriching students' real-world insights.
5. Future researchers may consider the same instrument used in this study to assess work immersion's performance level in public senior high schools in other regions of the country. Evaluate the curriculum for alignment with industry needs and assess programs in public schools with the aim of enhancing the work immersion program.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher prioritized ethical considerations throughout the study. To ensure transparency and obtain necessary permissions, formal letters were sent to the Department of Education (DepEd) CALABARZON Region and Schools Division Superintendents, seeking approval to

conduct the survey. Subsequently, the researcher obtained further ethical guidance by involving the dissertation adviser and experts for instrument evaluation. Feedback from these professionals guided amendments to the questionnaire, ensuring its reliability and relevance. All communications, including the finalized instrument presented through a Google form link, were documented for transparency. In respecting participants' rights, respondents were fully informed and voluntarily participated in the survey. The collected data underwent meticulous handling, including tallying, coding, collating, and tabulating, with analysis carried out using appropriate statistical tools. This comprehensive approach to ethical considerations reinforces the integrity and credibility of the research process.

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